

Report on EU level cross-visit activities of the Oper8 thematic network (Year 1)

WPI T1.3: Expansion of the Oper8 NNs to an EU-wide entity
Deliverable 1.3

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Document Information

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TABLE 1 - DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributors
1	13/11/2023	Draft V1	First version written by IFV with AUA, USC, and UNIPI contributions	IFV, AUA, USC, UNIPI
2	22/11/2023	Draft V2	Edits of reviewers' comments	IFV, USC, AUA
3	27/11/2023	Final	Final changes before submission	IFV, AUA

TABLE 2: DOCUMENT HISTORY

Abbreviations

KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS		
NNO	NATIONAL NETWORK OPERATOR		
NN	NATIONAL NETWORK		
WP	WORK PACKAGE		
OG	OPERATIONAL GROUP		

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

Participants

Participants		Contact
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TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS

Document summary

This document provides reports about all European cross-visit activities held during Year 1 of Oper8 project. It includes three in-person meetings, in Greece for the Kick-off meeting, Spain for the NNOs training, and Italy for the 1st Annual Project Meeting; and two webinars for online gatherings, focusing on identified solutions for weed control. This document starts with an introduction about Oper8 cross-visits and cross-fertilization challenges and ends with a Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and comments section summarizing this first year of fulfilments.

Executive Summary

Several EU-level events, both in person and virtual, have been organized during Year 1 of Oper8 project. These events have provided a deep insight into one or several alternative weed control solutions, thanks to farm demonstrations, and presentations of results, technical information, and feedback from practitioners. These activities aimed at enhancing cross-fertilization between Oper8 members and towards alternative weed control community. Three cross-border visits have been organized, gathering Oper8 members in person. Additionally, two virtual gatherings have been organized in a webinar format, bringing together Oper8 members and experts' panel, as well as external stakeholders.

Cross-border visits were organized back-to-back with the in-person project meetings. The first one took place during Oper8 kick-off meeting in Athens, Greece, in October 2022, and the last one took place during the first annual project meeting in Pisa, Italy, in October 2023. One additional visit, dedicated to the National Network Operators (NNOs) training, was organized in February 2023. The Pisa cross-visit gathered Oper8 experts' panel as they were invited to the first European workshop for assessment of alternative solutions.

Multiple solutions have been presented during these activities, at on-farm and experimental scales: hot foam thermal solution, natural herbicide use and development (on-field and in vitro stages), UAV data collection for weed identification, dead mulching with under-row plastic sheeting in vineyards, sheep grazing for high-quality wood production in forestry, spontaneous and sowed cover crops (soil coverage) for vineyards.

In-person field visits and webinars were complementary as they allowed Oper8 partners to reach various target groups, and gave different kinds of practical, technical, and scientific information. In total, between 11 October 2022, and 24 October 2023, 292 people took part in the different EU-level Oper8 activities.

Document content

Part. 1 Introduction on European level cross-visits

1.1 European level activities

European level cross-fertilization is one of the core objectives of European projects, as it allows members to meet, discuss, share, and learn from peers coming from other countries. Different kinds of activities have been defined for the 3 years of the project, all focusing on presentations and demonstrations about alternative weed control solutions and challenges.

In person cross-visits have been settled back-to-back with project meetings to avoid additional flights and fees. It consists in visiting demo-farm all together, with discussion and presentations around alternative weed control solutions. They can be on-farm visits, and experimental field demonstrations. All Oper8 members are invited to join and discuss about Oper8 works and alternative weed control. Observing practical solutions being used in experimental or real farms illustrates and helps understanding thoroughly challenges of each solution.

Virtual gatherings help Oper8 members and relevant stakeholders to meet more often around alternative weed control presentations. It was decided to follow a webinar format to be able to reach a large audience thanks to an open invitation widely spread by all Oper8 members. Presentations give feedback, trial results, key points, and other specific technical information, aiming at providing a top-of-the edge information to all participants.

1.2 Experts' panel and stakeholders' involvement

Oper8 EU-wide entity includes all stakeholders involved in National Networks (NNs), that NNOs are continuously building up and widening. It also includes Oper8 members and a specific experts' panel, consisting of two experts by member country. It has been created to have dedicated people specializing in alternative weed control topics, able to follow and take part regularly in the Oper8 activities. These experts bring applied, technical, or scientific knowledge and are asked to take part in multiple Oper8 activities, at both national and European levels. Experts are giving feedback and providing National and European networks with their expertise. Experts have been participating in focus groups and surveys within each country (WP2), webinars (WP1), and most of them attended the first European workshop (WP3) and the cross-visit (WP1) in Pisa during the first annual project meeting of the Oper8 project. A list of the current experts' panel is available in Table 5.

Other stakeholders have been reached during the webinars, thanks to the open invitation format to all interested people. It consequently helped the uptake of information within the different regions and target groups.

TABLE 5: EXPERTS' PANEL DURING YEAR 1

Country	National expert first name / last name	Organization name and type	Area of expertise	Title, main activities	European workshop 1	Webinar 1	Webinar 2
France	Laure Gontier	IFV	cover crops, soil functioning and fertility, soil biodiversity	Scientist, project manager in agronomy and soil management Viticulture engineering, experiments, trials, training sessions, national projects	n	n	y
France	Christophe Gaviglio	IFV	agriculture robotics, mechanical tools, mechanical weeding, herbicides use and herbicide reduction strategy, farming techniques management	Scientist, project manager Viticulture engineering, experiments, trials, training sessions, national projects	y	y	n
Latvia	Jevgēnija Nečajeva	PPRI "Agrihorti" (LLU)	weed biology, general aspects of weed control issues, soil seed bank, integrated management	Scientist, experiments, trials, training sessions, national and European projects in areas of expertise	y	y	y
Latvia	Maira Dzelzkalēja-Burmistre	Farmers Parliament	Sustainable farming and rural development, investments in farming industry, agricultural/rural development policies	Farmers Parliament Vice Chair, agriculture and rural development strategy, international relations, cooperation with stakeholders	n	n	n
Latvia	Eliza Ilze Malcieniece	Farmers Parliament	Vegetables, Weed control, sustainable farming	Farmer	y	y	y
UK	James Clarke	RSK ADAS	sustainable and integrated farming, weed control	Research Director	y	y	n
UK	Sarah Cook	RSK ADAS	Weed control, IPM	Senior Research Scientist	y	y	y
Greece	Ioannis Gazoulis	AUA	cover crops, weed management	Researcher	y	y	y
Greece	Nikolaos Antonopoulos	AUA	non chemical weed management	Researcher	y	y	y
Italy	Anna Camilla Moonen	Scuola Sant'Anna/University	weed biology and ecology, integrated weed management, Agroecological Crop Management and Crop Protection, Evaluation of cropping system sustainability	Associate professor, experiments, trials, teaching, national and European projects, communication office European Weed Research Society	y	y	n
Italy	Danilo Marandola	CREA-PB/Research Council of Italian Ministry of Agriculture	agricultural policies, rural development, conservation agriculture, sustainable agriculture	Scientist, agro-climatic action working group coordinator for RDP at national level	y	n	y
Sweden	Agneta Sundgren	Jordbruksverket (Swedish Board of Agriculture).	Weed management particularly in horticultural crops	Advisor weed management	y	n	n
Sweden	Jonas Schon	USC	vineyard weed management	Researcher	y	n	y
Spain	Julian Garcia Berríos	USC	vineyard weed and pest management	Researcher	y	y	n
Spain	Cristina Cabaleiro Sobrino	USC	vineyard weed and pest management	Researcher	y	n	n
Spain	Victor Manuel Boga Vázquez	Mel Finca Orgánica, SCG.	Agriculture and Beekeeping	Practitioner	y	n	y

Part. 2 Demo-farm cross-border visits

2.1 Demo-event during Oper8 kick-off meeting - Athens, Greece

2.1.1 Demonstration event information

Date: 11 October 2022.

Location: Experimental farm of the Laboratory of Agronomy, Agricultural University of Athens.

Attendees: All Oper8 partners participating in the kick-off meeting.

After the kick-off meeting presentations and discussions on the management of Work Packages (WP) and tasks, a demonstration event was carried out by the weed experts, Prof. Ilias Travlos and his team, at the Laboratory of Agronomy of the Agricultural University of Athens.

2.1.2 Demonstration of alternative weed control solutions and trials

The duration of the event was 2 hours. The attendees had the opportunity to observe small-scale field trials and pot experiments where alternative weed control methods were performed and evaluated compared to conventional practices, especially synthetic herbicides (see details below). During the cross-visit, the Oper8 partners had the opportunity to participate in the following solution demonstrations.

2.1.2.1 Live demonstration of one thermal weed control method

The weed experts applied hot foam to annual and perennial summer weed species, using an oil-consumed machine Foamstream (WeedingTech, UK), which was stored in the facilities of the Laboratory of Agronomy. Hot foam is a novel method that is used mainly against noxious weeds in urban and peri-urban areas, as an alternative to chemical herbicides.

FIGURE 1: HOT FOAM WEEDING SOLUTION DEMONSTRATION, AUA.

Its utilization has increased in the last years due to its compatibility with the EU Green Deal targets and the demand for herbicide input reduction. During this event, the NNO Prof. Ilias Travlos and his team of experts informed participants about the method's range of applications, suitability for various farming systems, technical intricacies, and its potential for weed management across different crops. This speech enabled the participants to discuss and assess the method, as they could compare the weed control results of the operation with the outcome of an application with hot foam that was performed two days before the demonstration. A dedicated discussion addressed its efficacy against perennial invasive plant species, and specifically *Solanum elaeagnifolium*, with weed experts explaining the optimal time for the operation is based on the weed's growth stage.

2.1.2.2 Assessment of the effect of natural herbicides against summer weeds

The participants were informed about the effect of pelargonic acid against common summer weeds and noxious invasive plant species. Pelargonic acid is a contact herbicide that has gained the attention of weed researchers globally as an ideal substitute and/or alternative of synthetic herbicides, as it has a knockdown effect against any weed and has no residual activity. Discussions were held between the Oper8 members regarding the applicability, the utilization, and the value of natural herbicides in modern agriculture, which needs to become greener and more sustainable.

FIGURE 2: DISCUSSION ABOUT WEED CONTROL SOLUTIONS.

2.1.2.3 Real time drone flight and data collection

The participants had the opportunity to see first-hand how a drone can fly over a field and collect valuable spatial data of weed distribution by using specific vegetation indices and exploiting models. The precision agriculture experts of the Smart Farming team of the Agricultural University of Athens explained the technical details of drone flights, the vegetation indices that are used in this type of operations, the challenges, and the opportunities in the use of unmanned aerial vehicles for weed management. A half-hour discussion took place about the potential combination of cultural practices and alternative weed control methods with drones and weed mapping to assist site-specific weed management.

2.2 Demo-event during NNO training - Lugo, Spain

2.2.1 Demonstration event information

FIGURE 3: NNOS VISITED USC EXPERIMENTAL GREENHOUSES.

Date: 1-2 February 2023

Location: Galicia, Spain. Organized by the University of Santiago de Compostela.

Attendees: All participants to in person NNO training.

On the first day of the NNO training meeting, NNOs visited the greenhouses in which the USC and the different plant production department research groups, perform experiments on crop development, as well as other treatments to manage crops, including potential weeding treatments. The second day of this training session was fully dedicated to demo-farm visits.

2.2.2 Demonstration of alternative weed control solutions and trials

2.2.2.1 Plastic sheeting and complementary solutions in vineyards

As aforementioned, during the first field visit attendees inspected a vineyard in the village of Portomarín (Lugo – NW Spain). The USC professor of the viticulture and crop health department Julián García Berrios made a presentation of the treatments applied for weeding removal in a vineyard that mirror the traditional viticulture system in Galicia. Thus, Prof. Berrios explained physical methods to avoid weeding and plant competition with vines without using herbicides, such as plastic sheeting for weeds. In this way, weeds can be removed and avoid their future appearance by means of avoiding solar radiation reaching the soil by covering it with a tarp, producing weeds to die off and not replicating. Even considering plastic sheets are not an eco-friendly material, the re-usage or long-term use of this material, make it sustainable since it can last for many years, as Prof. Berrios highlighted with the ones installed in this vineyard around 20 years ago. Also, it facilitates the use of bioherbicides as a complement for full weeding removal. In addition, it has been acknowledged that black tarps help to preserve soil moisture and raise soil temperature, thus increasing crop productivity. Moreover, this system avoids fuel use, labour hours and soil compaction from heavy machinery usage.

FIGURE 4: OPER8 CROSS-VISIT PARTICIPANTS IN A VINEYARD INCLUDING NON-CHEMICAL WEEDING METHODS.

2.2.2.2 Sheep grazing in high-quality timber production plantations

FIGURE 5: VISIT OF BOSQUES NATURALES S.A. FACILITIES WITH HIGH QUALITY TIMBER TREES AND SHEEP GRAZING.

After visiting the vineyard, attendees travelled to Boimorto (A Coruña – NW Spain), a village close to Santiago de Compostela where the company Bosques Naturales S.A. has facilities allocated to high-quality timber production of walnut and cherry trees. Several years ago, the company contacted the Silvopast Research Group of the USC (partner of the Oper8 project) for reducing their consumption of glyphosate, in order to avoid the ecological problematics linked to its usage, and other potential harmful effects for environment and health, but also the burden on the company economic balance sheet. As part of the visit, it was noticed by the participants that the effect of glyphosate on soil coverage still lasts after ten years since its last application. Thus, in collaboration with the USC, an experiment with sheep started for weeding removal, considering sheep to be a great input for maintaining low biomass after a first mechanical treatment. The preliminary experiments were really successful and made the company to increase the number of sheep up to 500 heads turning the expenses on glyphosate into incomes from lambs' commercialization and selling of other products such as sheep manure.

2.3 Demo-event during the first Oper8 annual project meeting - Pisa, Italy

2.3.1 Demonstration event information

Date: 23-24 October 2023

Location: Pisa region, Italy. Day 1: Castellani farm in Pecciola, Pisa. Day 2: Monterosola farm in Volterra, Pisa.

Attendees: All participants to the first annual project meeting participated to these two Pisa cross-visits, including several experts, as they were invited to participate in the first European workshop (WP3) for evaluation of weed control solutions.

2.3.2 Demonstration of alternative weed control solutions and trials

2.3.2.1 Cover crops between the rows for vineyards.

During the first day of the project meeting in Pisa, and after the morning plenary session, all partners attended the first cross visit at Castellani farm, Pisa, an organic winery farm where they were welcomed by Alessandro Moretto, the agronomist in charge. The duration of the event was 2 hours, during which attendees had the opportunity to listen to Alessandro's experience using alternative methods for weed control, such as cover crops and their mechanical devitalization. More precisely, he manages the vine alternating rows with a permanent spontaneous ground cover, with rows sown in the fall with a cool-season mixture of cover crops, i.e., facelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth), vetch (*Vicia pannonica* Crantz) and triticale (× *Triticosecale*). The mixture is kept growing during the winter not competing with the vines, and then in spring (May), when vetch and phacelia are flowered (at least 70%) and triticale is at the early milk stage, it is mechanically devitalized using a roller crimper, remaining on the ground during the summer as a dead mulch. The mulch allows to maintain a good humidity and a lower temperature of the soil, also obtaining a good weed suppression due the physical obstacles. This interesting topic stimulated the curiosity of the attendees that led a discussion, focused on especially the effects of this technique on the vine growth and diseases, but Alessandro confirmed that no increasing in diseases nor in competition were observed in his production context. Afterwards, together with our expert in farm mechanization, prof. Christian Frascioni, showcased the machines used in the farm for the management of the weeds and the cover crops. Among these, the innovative roller crimper built by Dondi s.r.l., called "Rotovitis" that has the possibility to increase its weight adding ballasts to improve the devitalization of the most productive cover crops producing a large amount of biomass. Other interesting machinery showed were the rollhacker and the finger weeder, tools developed for the under row weed management. In conclusion, Dr. Lorenzo Gagliardi, a PhD student in farm mechanization at Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment, UNIPI, delivered a presentation concerning some trials that the Oper8 partner UNIPI research group carries on at Castellani farm, using the innovative machinery presented before. On this regard, the first trial was about different strategies for the under row weed control using combinations of the tools presented before (compared with traditional mechanical methods), while the second one regarded the use of the roller crimper "with" and "without" ballasts to evaluate the capacity of devitalization of the cover crops.

FIGURE 6: PICTURES OF THE FIRST CROSS-VISIT AT CASTELLANI FARM, ITALY

2.3.2.2 Subterranean clover cover crop under the grapevine row for vineyards.

During the second day of the meeting, and before the European Expert Panel Workshop, attendees visited the vine farm partner of the Italian Operational Group (OG) "IO-CONCIV", in Monterosola farm in Volterra, Pisa. Michele Senesi, the agronomist of the farm, and the owner presented the farm, and then Professor Daniele Antichi showed the field trial that focused on the under row ground-cover through a self-reseeding subterranean clover crop. Daniele, talking about the research experience of the OG, highlighted how the cover crops can deliver important agroecosystem services: e.g., improving soil fertility, reducing soil erosion and weed presence, increasing carbon, nitrogen input and biodiversity. The shown innovation implies the introduction of a self-reseeding cover crop under the row, coupled with a cover crop mixture sown on alternated rows, to reduce the tillage intensity. In fact, this farm is being certified organic, so herbicides aren't the reference system. Daniele detailed as the innovative process consists of sowing subterranean clover under the rows in autumn after the grape harvest (in Monterosola conditions, early winter was also possible), once every 3 or 4 years, and keeping it growing up until late spring-early summer, when the clover dies and releases the seeds directly into the soil by geocarp. The biomass of the clover will cover the soil in autumn, winter and spring as living mulch and in summer as dead mulch, thus not competing at all with vines for water and nutrients. At the end of the summer, with the first rainfall, the clover seeds spontaneously germinate, and a new biological cycle will start under the rows, with benefits in terms of contrasting weed emergence and soil fertility improvement (i.e., by organic matter increase/conservation, reduced soil erosion and increased N availability). In terms of constraints, Daniele explained the more important limit was the mechanization of the seeding, because the farms involved in the OG have sown the cover by hand, although there are on the market some examples of seeder properly adjusted to seed under the row.

FIGURE 7: PICTURES OF THE SECOND CROSS VISIT AT MONTEROSOLA FARM, ITALY.

Part. 3 Virtual gatherings

3.1 Set up of the webinar methodology

The aim of these virtual gatherings was enhancing cross-fertilization between Oper8 stakeholders, similarly to the in person cross-visits. As a virtual gathering event, it was decided together with AUA and IFV to have webinar style online events, to gather and disseminate relevant information coming from Oper8 OG and Oper8 members' expertise to a wide audience.

The webinars were set up twice in the year 2023, in a time-limited format: 1 hour to 1.5 hour. The first webinar topic was electrical weeding, an innovative solution newly commercialized, undergoing trials in several of Oper8 partners' works. Various speakers took part, giving feedback and results from their trials for several crops, and an industry representative external Oper8 partner completed some of the result presentations. The second webinar was about cover crop, a wide topic being not only a weed control solution, but also a multi-beneficial and multi-purpose practice for farming. Presentations were selected to be complementary, along with a general presentation about cover crop use and requirements, then focusing on technical information and challenges for various crops. An external speaker involved in CliMed-Fruit H2020 EU-project gave cover crop information from a climate change perspective.

Thanks to satisfaction surveys, comments from participants, both Oper8 members and external stakeholders, are being taken into consideration to improve the next webinars. The webinar format allowed to have an open invitation that all Oper8 members spread in their own networks, reaching all target groups within EU and not only in Oper8 involved countries. All Oper8 members are participating in the choice of the webinar topic by giving suggestions, and all are requested to take part as speakers or by inviting relevant speakers from their country or organization. All were highly involved, and no difficulties occurred to define a successful program for both events.

3.2 First webinar in April 2023

3.2.1 1st webinar description

This first virtual gathering for Oper8 T1.3 was an open invitation webinar held on Wednesday, 26 April 2023, at 11 am CEST. It focused on Electrical Weeding as an alternative weed control solution. An introduction about Oper8 project and alternative weed control challenge was presented in the first part of the webinar by AUA. Then, 4 presentations have been focusing on Electrical weeding (see below Program and speakers). The aim of this first virtual gathering was to have

experts and Oper8 partners presenting and sharing their work on Electrical Weeding to i) Oper8 experts, ii) NNOs, iii) other Oper8 partners iv) AKIS ecosystems actors and relevant stakeholders. This is part of the technical and scientific transfer and uptake goal within Europe of the Oper8 project.

3.2.2 Webinar set up and preparation

One virtual meeting was held for discussion and preparation between the speakers and the organizers on 13 April 2023.

Emma Lönn (Agrovast) and Camille Guilbert (IFV) developed communication support for the event: Oper8 e-newsletter, a pdf document for flyer, posts on social media through Oper-8 accounts, events' section of Oper8 website. These communication supports have been sent to the Oper8 partners and NNOs to send out widely the invitation to their own professional networks, Oper8 NNs, and other relevant contact through emailing, and social media posting and reposting. A registration number follow-up was sent 3 times before the event to encourage people to communicate about the event.

Registrations were done through a Microsoft Form including a pre-webinar survey with a required consent form agreement. At the end of the survey, the GoToWebinar platform link was available to complete the registration.

3.2.3 Webinar run

The webinar was broadcasted through the GoToWebinar platform, using IFV subscription. It was coordinated and chaired by Camille Guilbert (IFV), and the GoToWebinar platform manager was Emma Corben (IFV). The title was 'Solutions for alternative weed control #1: Electric weeding - Case studies in vineyard, grassland, and fruit production.' It lasted between 11:00 am and 12:00 pm.

Program and speakers are presented below:

1. Introduction on alternative weed control challenge and Oper8 project / Ilias Travlos and Nicoleta Darra, Agricultural University of Athens (Greece)
2. Electric weeding in grassland and fruit production / Lynn Tatnell and Kevin Godfrey, ADAS (UK)
3. Electric weeding machinery development / Tom Archer, RootWave company (UK)
4. Electric weeding in vineyard / Christophe Gaviglio, French Wine and Vine Institute IFV (France)

The last 15 minutes have been dedicated to answering attendees' questions.

3.2.4 Post-webinar follow-up

All documents related to this first virtual gathering, such as PowerPoint slides and the list of participants providing all data about participants, are available in the dedicated folder Virtual gathering No1 ('WP1/T1.3/Virtual gatherings/Virtual gathering No1' Oper8 folder). The webinar has been recorded and is available on Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aNzDHTUzuDg>

The total number of registrations reached 207, with lots of late registrations just before the event, among UK participants, possibly from Rootwave company and ADAS networks. The effective number of attendees was 122. It appears that many people are interested in this topic but could not attend. Most target group categories were represented, except EIP-AGRI and CAP networks, but these people might have been counted in other categories. Moreover, only one person was counted in the citizens / consumers category. Communication means for this open invitation have been aiming at networks involved in this topic through professional networks, social media, emailing, and national networks. These virtual gatherings are mainly focusing on technical information and knowledge exchanges, and are not designed specifically for the public, what could explain the low representativeness of this category. Policymakers came mainly from the UK.

FIGURE 8: REGISTRATION NUMBERS PIE CHART, FOR OPER8

FIGURE 9: ATTENDEE NUMBERS PIE CHART, FOR OPER8 COUNTRIES, EUROPE, OUT OF EUROPE, AND UNKNOWN.

TABLE 6: TARGET GROUP CATEGORIES REACHED, BASED ON THE REGISTRATION LIST.

Target group among registrations	France	Greece	Italy	Latvia	Spain	Sweden	UK	other - Europe	other - non Europe	unknown	TOTAL
Farmers / Cooperatives	6	3	2	5	5	1	5	8	1	0	36
Advisors / Consulting companies	5	5	0	1	2	0	8	8	0	0	29
Agri-food industry	1	5	0	0	4	2	2	4	0	0	18
Research community	7	13	12	8	9	6	21	16	4	0	96
Policymakers	0	0	2	2	0	0	8	0	0	0	12
Citizens / Consumers	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
EIP-AGRI and CAP networks	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
other	1	4	0	0	2	1	2	3	0	2	15
TOTAL	20	31	16	16	22	10	46	39	5	2	207

A satisfaction survey has been sent after the workshop to all attendees, asking for general opinion, but also for topic of interest for next webinar. The results of the 13 answers are available in Table 7.

TABLE 7: 1ST WEBINAR SATISFACTION SURVEY REPORT (SCORES ARE OUT OF 5).

Total respondent number		13
Average opinion about the webinar	Average opinion about the format	
4,2	4,4	
Participation to the next webinar ?		
Yes		10
It depends on the topic		3
Other topic to address ?		
Cover crops		9
Robots		8
Computerized identification of weeds (drone technology...)		10
Physical solutions (thermal weed control, mechanical weed control...)		11
Participated in the Oper8 survey on needs, gaps & barriers ?		
Yes		8
No		5
Participation in future Oper8 activities (demo events, meeting, workshops)		
Yes		8
No		0
Maybe		5

A list of suggested topics and comments, coming from the satisfaction survey, is available below:

- Low hectare dose/spot and/or band application of herbicides.
- Carbon footprints of the various alternative systems compared to existing conventional chemistry and whether the alternative worsen or help the climate crisis.
- Integrating chemical and non-chemical options
- Understanding barriers to adoption of alternatives and determining ways to overcome them
- Even if a trial is a proof of concept, it is very important to have economic information such as machine and use costs. Field expectations are mostly about efficiency and costs.

As a conclusion, the general opinion on this first virtual gathering was positive, and all countries have been involved before and during the webinar, by inviting all kinds of stakeholders, and participating in the presentations. It was decided the next webinar would follow the same organization, with minor modifications such as number of speakers and duration of the event.

3.3 Second webinar in October 2023

3.3.1 2nd webinar description

This second Oper8 webinar was held on Thursday, 19 November 2023 at 11 am CEST. It was part of the virtual cross-visits aiming at cross-fertilization between EU partners. Following the first event on 26 April, focusing on Electrical weeding, this second online event was focusing on cover crops. Speakers presented cover crops use as an alternative weed control solution through general challenges, feedback, trial results, technical specificities.

3.3.2 Webinar set up and preparation

A call for speaker email was sent on 21 August 2023. Previously, some informal discussions during WP1 meetings and a shared Excel file for suggestions helped choosing the topic. Identified speakers were gathered during an online meeting to build the program together, on 7 September. One other EU-H2020 project member was invited for connection with other related projects. She presented her cover crop experience and focused on some of CliMed-Fruit project topics.

A training meeting was held 30 minutes before the webinar to get used to GoToWebinar software.

Communication documents were produced by Emma Lonn (Agrovast) and Camille Guilbert (IFV) and sent to all Oper8 partners for broad diffusion and circulation in each country's networks. Below is the list of the diffusion means: newsletter sent to all people registered on the Oper8 newsletter mailing list, invitation and program on pdf document, multiple posts and reposts on social media by Oper8 social media and partner's social media, events' section of Oper8 website, raw registration link for other kind of communication in partner's channels such as company newsletter, flyer.

A registration number follow-up was sent 3 times before the event (26/09, 5/10, 11/10) to keep Oper8 members updated, and increase participation. Registrations were done through a Microsoft Form including a pre-webinar survey with a required consent form agreement. Each participant registered through Microsoft Form was then hand registered on GoToWebinar tool, due to consent form requirements, preventing from direct registration.

3.3.3 Webinar run

The webinar was broadcasted through the GoToWebinar platform (IFV subscription). Coordination and chairing by Camille Guilbert (IFV). GoToWebinar platform manager was Emma Corben (IFV). The title was 'Solutions for alternative weed control #2: Cover crops use across Europe.' It lasted between 11:00 am and 12:30 pm.

Program and speakers are presented below:

1. Needs, gaps and barriers; use of cover crops across Europe / Eleanor Dearlove, Integrated Pest Management Consultant - ADAS Sustainable Agricultural Systems - ADAS Gleadthorpe, United Kingdom.
2. Agronomic strategies for the introduction of cover crops in arable and field vegetable cropping systems / Daniele Antichi, Associate Professor in Agronomy and Crop Sciences - Centre for Agri-environmental Research "Enrico Avanzi" - University of Pisa, Italy.
3. The role of cover crop diversity and complementarity on weed management and ecosystem services in perennial crops (Olive, citrus, apple trees) / Ilias Travlos, Associate Professor - Agricultural University of Athens, Greece.
4. Agronomic strategies for the introduction of cover crops into winegrowing systems (Vineyard) / Laure Gontier, Project manager in Agronomy and Soil management - French Wine and Vine Institute IFV, France.
5. Machines for cover crop management (All crops) / Christian Frasconi, Associate Professor in Farm machinery and Farm mechanization - Center for Agri-environmental Research "Enrico Avanzi" - University of Pisa, Italy.
6. Practical experiences and innovation in progress on the use of cover crops in the North-East of Italy (Vegetables, vineyard, corn, soybean) / Cristina Micheloni, Senior researcher in Vinidea and President of AIAB FVG, Italy.

A brief introduction about Oper8 works, progress, and ongoing steps, was made by Camille Guilbert (IFV). Each presentation was followed by 2-5 minutes dedicated to answering attendees' questions.

3.3.4 Recording and reporting

All the documents related to this webinar are available in the dedicated Oper8 folder: WP1/T1.3/Virtual gatherings/Virtual gathering No2 WEBINAR2). The webinar has been recorded and is available on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TIDTZEbwWoc>

The list of participants and all PowerPoint presentations are available in the same dedicated folder. In the participant list, target group information has been completely completed by Oper8 members. Information about registrations, attendance, and target groups, is available in Figure 10, and Table 8. The total number of registrations reached 257, permanently increasing during the week before the event. It appears this cover crop topic raised interest from all crop sector and all kinds of target groups. The actual number of attendees was 104, and resulted in a successful event, with all target groups reached within Europe. Similarly, to the first event, some participants came from EU-countries not involved in Oper8 topic, what shows the different ways of communication are reaching a large audience, not limited to internal Oper8 countries.

FIGURE 10: LEFT PICTURE: REGISTRATION NUMBERS PIE CHART, FOR OPER8 COUNTRIES, EUROPE, AND OUT OF EUROPE. RIGHT PICTURE: PIE CHART OF PARTICIPANTS WHO ATTENDED THE WEBINAR, FOR OPER8 COUNTRIES, EUROPE, AND OUT OF EUROPE.

TABLE 8: TARGET GROUP OF ALL REGISTERED PEOPLE FOR WEBINAR ON COVER CROPS.

TARGET GROUP CATEGORY	France	Greece	Italy	Latvia	non-Europe	other - Europe	Spain	Sweden	UK	TOTAL
Advisors / Consulting companies	7		7	6	2	7	3	4	19	55
Agri-food industry	4	4	3			2	4	2	2	21
Citizens / Consumers	5	6			3	2				16
Farmers / Cooperatives	5		4	15		4	2	1	21	52
other	1				1	7			3	12
Research community	5	18	12	14	4	10	10	5	18	96
Polymakers							2	2		4
EIP-AGRI and CAP networks								1		1
TOTAL	27	28	26	35	10	32	21	15	63	257

A satisfaction survey was sent to participants, who were reminded to complete it in the beginning of the webinar. Participation rates were much higher than for the first webinar, with 53 respondents. The results are available in Table 9. Respondents were asked to give some comments and topic of interest for next webinars. Some of the suggestions are listed here: allelopathy, new environmentally friendly herbicides, alternative herbicides (low risk products, basic substances, botanicals), options for mechanical weed control, organic weed control, biodegradable mulch, presentation of different machines for vegetable crops for applying dead mulch or compost in crop beds (i.e. localized spreaders), or different machines for collecting organic matter (harvesters, collector crushers, grasshoppers, vacuum cleaners,) and obtaining material for mulching locally, guided cameras, drones, mechanical with artificial intelligence, cover crop direct seeding and management, and spontaneous weed cover management in rainfed olive groves, weeds as cover crops in no-till herbicide-free systems.

TABLE 9: 2ND WEBINAR SATISFACTION SURVEY REPORT

Total respondent number	53
Average opinion about the webinar (out of 5)	3,96
Average opinion about the format (out of 5)	4,19
Participation to next webinar?	
It depends on the topic	12
Yes	40
No	1
Participated in the past to other Oper activities?	
Yes	20
No	25
Oper8 demo-events	1
Survey on needs, gaps & barriers for adoption of alternative weed control solutions	5
Focus group meetings	1
Oper8 national networks	1

Part. 4 KPI follow-up and comments

4.1 Key performance indicators and attendance sheets

Lists of attendees at all EU-level cross-visit activities are available in the Annex chapter. A follow-up and summary of all events held during Year 1 is available in Table 10. Experts and other alternative weed control related stakeholders have been participating in these various cross-fertilization events.

TABLE 10: KPI 1.2 NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS IN CROSS-BORDER VISITS & VIRTUAL GATHERINGS.

Event	Date	Number of participants
KoM Cross-visit Athens Greece	11/10/2022	27
NNO 1st training session Lugo Spain	1-2/2/2023	13
1st virtual gathering of the NN experts and NN members Online - webinar #1	26/4/2023	122
2nd virtual gathering of the NN experts and NN members Online - webinar #2	19/10/2023	104
Project meeting with demo cross-visit Pisa, Italy	23-24/10/2023	30
	TOTAL:	292

4.2 Comments on EU-level cross-visit activities

Cross-border visits and webinars are complementary events aiming at increasing the uptake of alternative weed control, providing participants with top-of-the edge technical information, applied examples within various soil and weather conditions, discussion, and cross-fertilization.

KPI are on a good track for this first year, with participants from various target groups. General opinions about webinars have been positive, and many people came back for the second event. About the in-person cross-visits, it is a challenge to get people flying to foreign demo-farms, but most of the experts and other members could attend.

On the one hand, onsite cross-border visits are limited in terms of the number of people who can attend, but give a deep insight into the solution being tested and allow participants to discuss around this topic all together. On the other hand, webinars virtual gatherings are less concrete than a demo field visit and do not allow participants discussion, but they lead to a higher number of participants. During these webinars, the English language remains a barrier for many participants, preventing them from registering. National activities are consequently complementary to these limited-scale European gatherings, for example with national demo-events and workshops, reaching many local context stakeholders, and transferring information and knowledge between target groups. Also, participants might prefer getting information only about the crop they have expertise in, for example during webinars; but it is considered more useful and increasing cross-fertilization to have presentations about multiple crops, that is why it has not been decided to have specific crop presentations.

Additionally, communication activities (WP5) and production of audio-visual materials (WP4) help reaching farmers, advisors, and other practitioners, who are looking for alternative solutions adapted to their needs and constraints, for a longer period, as they will remain available after Oper8 project is over.

Annex 1: List of participants - Demo-event Athens, Greece

No	Partner	Name	Participation
1	AUA	Spyros Fountas	Onsite
2	AUA	Ilias Travlos	Onsite
3	AUA	Nicoleta Darra	Onsite
4	AUA	George Tsiantis	Onsite
5	AUA	Alex Tataridas	Onsite
6	AUA	Giannis Gazoulis	Onsite
7	AUA	Olga Kriezi	Onsite
8	AUA	Erato Lazarou	Onsite
9	AUA	Konstantina Argiropoulou	Onsite
10	AUA	Giolanda Giakoumatou	Onsite
11	AUA	Nikos Antonopoulos	Onsite
12	AUA	Hercules Panoutsopoulos	Onsite
13	AUA	Matina Voulgaraki	Onsite
14	AUA	Kalliopi Kounani	Onsite
15	USC	Javier R Riguier	Onsite
16	USC	Rosa Mosquera	Onsite
17	USC	Javier Santiago	Onsite
18	UNIFI	Daniele Antichi	Onsite
19	LLU	Maksims Filipovičs	Onsite
20	LLU	Janis Jasko	Online
21	LLU	Viktorija Zagorska	Online
22	AGROVAST	Thomas Börjesson	Onsite
23	IFV	Camille Guilbert	Onsite
24	IFV	Hugo Eirios	Online
25	IFV	Prezman Fanny	Online
26	ZSA	Inga Berzina	Onsite
27	ZSA	Iveta Grudovska	Onsite
28	AGROMET	Dora Angelopoulou	Onsite
29	ADAS	Lynn Tatnell	Onsite
30	ADAS	Will John	Onsite
31	ADAS	Ellie Dearlove	Onsite
32	PO	Celine Choquer	Online

Only onsite people took part in the demonstration, but participants discussed about alternative weed control during the event.

Annex 2: List of participants - Demo-event Galicia, Spain

Organisation	Attendees
AUA	Nicoleta Darra (on-line)
	Ilias Travlos
	Kiki Kontogeorgou
ZSA	Inga Berzina
ADAS	Kevin Godfrey (on-line)
	Lynn Tatnell
UNIPI	Lorenzo Tramacere
IFV	Camille Guilbert
USC	Julián Díaz Berrios
	María Rosa Mosquera Losada
	Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro
	Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez
AGROVAST	Mats Emilson (on-line)

Only onsite people took part in the demonstration, but participants discussed about alternative weed control during the event.

Annex 3: List of participants - Demo-event Pisa, Italy

Name	Surname	Participation role	presence/online
Daniele	Antichi	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Nikolaos	Antonopoulos	National Expert	In presence
Inga	Berzina	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Thomas	Börjesson	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Victor Manuel	Boga	National Expert	In presence
GAVIGLIO	Christophe	National Expert	Online
Sarah	Cook	National Expert	In presence
Nicoleta	Darra	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Eleanor	Dearlove	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Maksims	Fiļipovičs	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Christian	Frasconi	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Lorenzo	Gagliardi	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Julian	Garcia Berrios	National Expert	In presence
Marta Beatriz	Garcia Villar	National Expert	In presence
IOANNIS	GAZOULIS	National Expert	In presence
Kevin	Godfrey	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Iveta	Grudovska	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Camille	Guilbert	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Olga	Kriezi	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
PARASKEVI	LE TSA	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Elīza Ilze	Malceniece	National Expert	In presence
Danilo	Marandola	National Expert	In presence
Camilla	Moonen	National Expert	In presence
Maria Rosa	Mosquera Losada	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Francisco Javier	Rodriguez Rigueiro	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Jose Javier	Santiago Freijanes	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Jonas	Schon	National Expert	Online
Agneta	Sundgren	National Expert	In presence
Lynn	Tatnell	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Lorenzo	Tramacere	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Ilias	Travlos	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	Online
Charlotta	Wångdahl	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	Online
Viktorija	Zagorska	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence
Aristodimos	Zamidis	Member of Oper8 Partner Institution	In presence

Annex 4: List of participants - Webinar #1 Electrical weeding

Anonymized names	Attended the webinar	Occupation	Target group	Country grouped
N1	YES		Research community	UK
N2	YES		Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N3	YES		Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N4	YES	agronomist	Agri-food industry	Greece
N5	YES	Academia	Research community	Italy
N6	YES	Farmer	Research community	Greece
N7	YES	Future land owner	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N8	YES	Professor in Agronomy	Research community	Italy
N9	YES	Project Manager	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia
N10	YES	Kubota ICE	Agri-food industry	other - Europe
N11	YES	Project manager	Research community	Sweden
N12	YES	Organic tillage specialist	Research community	other - Europe
N13	YES	Pilot and drone pilot	Agri-food industry	Sweden
N14	YES		Research community	UK
N15	YES		other	unknown
N16	YES		Research community	UK
N17	YES	Junior Onderzoeker	Research community	other - Europe
N18	YES	Farm Manager	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N19	YES		Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europe
N20	YES	journalist	other	Spain
N21	YES	Reseracher	Research community	Italy
N22	YES	Journalist	other	UK
N23	YES	Research Director	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N24	YES	Principal scientist	Research community	UK
N25	YES	Agricultural Entomologist	Research community	UK
N26	YES		Research community	UK
N27	YES	Environmental engineer	Farmers / Cooperatives	France
N28	YES	Agronomist	Research community	Greece
N29	YES	Agronomist	Research community	Greece
N30	YES	Agronomist & consultant	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N31	YES	IPM Consultant	Research community	UK
N32	YES	Pesticide regulator	Policymakers	UK
N33	YES		Research community	UK
N34	YES	AHDB Knowledge Exchange Manager	Policymakers	UK
N35	YES		Research community	UK
N36	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	Greece
N37	YES		Research community	UK
N38	YES	Plant manager	Agri-food industry	Spain
N39	YES	Researcher	Research community	Spain
N40	YES	research	Research community	Latvia
N41	YES	Associate Professor of the University of Pisa	Research community	Italy
N42	YES	Ingeniero Agrónomo	Research community	Spain
N43	YES	Research	Research community	other - Europe
N44	YES	PHD student	Research community	Italy
N45	YES	Researcher, grapegrower	Research community	Spain
N46	YES		Research community	France
N47	YES	Asesora de explotacions Enxeñeira técnica agrícola	Advisors / Consulting companies	Spain
N48	YES	Crop Protection Scientist	Policymakers	UK
N49	YES	agricultural expert	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia

Anonymized names	Attended the webinar	Occupation	Target group	Country grouped
N50	YES	Crop Research Consultant	Research community	UK
N51	YES		Research community	UK
N52	YES	Agronomist	Research community	Sweden
N53	YES	Researcher sustainable agriculture	Research community	other - Europe
N54	YES	Crop Protection Scientist	Policymakers	UK
N55	YES	researcher	Research community	other - Europe
N56	YES		other	other - Europe
N57	YES		Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europe
N58	YES	weed Control Development Specialist	Agri-food industry	UK
N59	YES	Researcher	Research community	Latvia
N60	YES	projectleader	Research community	Sweden
N61	YES	Chargée de mission développement durable et œnotourisme	Farmers / Cooperatives	France
N62	YES	Advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	Greece
N63	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	Greece
N64	YES	Organic Specialist, Farmer	Research community	other - Europe
N65	YES	Research Associate	Research community	Greece
N66	YES		Farmers / Cooperatives	Sweden
N67	YES	Agronomist, Plant Science student	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia
N68	YES	farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia
N69	YES	Researcher	Research community	Greece
N70	YES	Researcher	Research community	other - Europe
N71	YES		Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N72	YES	researcher	Research community	Sweden
N73	YES	Horticulturalist	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N74	YES	Organic Advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europe
N75	YES	Regulatory Scientist	Policymakers	UK
N76	YES	Senior Consultant	Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europe
N77	YES	Associate Professor	Research community	Italy
N78	YES	Assistant Farm Environment Adviser	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N79	YES	Organic Advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europe
N80	YES	Researcher	Research community	Greece
N81	YES	researcher	Research community	Latvia
N82	YES	Journalist Lantbrukets Affärer	other	Sweden
N83	YES		Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europe
N84	YES	Lecturer	Research community	other - Europe
N85	YES	Farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	other - Europe
N86	YES	Agricultor	Farmers / Cooperatives	Spain
N87	YES	Wine advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	France
N88	YES		other	unknown
N89	YES	post-doc researcher	Research community	Italy
N90	YES	Researcher, asociated professor	Research community	Latvia
N91	YES	Researcher	Research community	Italy
N92	YES	Farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	other - Europe
N93	YES		other	UK
N94	YES	PROFESOR EMÉRITO	Research community	Spain

Anonymized names	Attended the webinar	Occupation	Target group	Country grouped
N95	YES	Researcher	Research community	Sweden
N96	YES		Research community	UK
N97	YES	Researcher	Research community	Spain
N98	YES	Commercial manager	Agri-food industry	Spain
N99	YES	Researcher	Research community	Spain
N100	YES	Strategic Developer	Agri-food industry	other - Europe
N101	YES	Chargée de Mission Innovation, FR CUMA Occitanie	Farmers / Cooperatives	France
N102	YES	Technician University of Pisa	Research community	Italy
N103	YES	projectmanager	other	other - Europe
N104	YES	Crop Pathology Consultant	Research community	UK
N105	YES	Farm engagement Officer	Research community	UK
N106	YES	technician	Farmers / Cooperatives	France
N107	YES	Export Sales Manager	Farmers / Cooperatives	Italy
N108	YES	Agronomist	Agri-food industry	Greece
N109	YES	AG drone operator	Agri-food industry	Sweden
N110	YES		Research community	UK
N111	YES	Architect Engineer	Citizens / Consumers	Greece
N112	YES	Researcher	Research community	Greece
N113	YES	PhD students in agricultural sciences	Research community	Italy
N114	YES	consultant	Advisors / Consulting companies	Latvia
N115	YES	Farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	other - Europe
N116	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europe
N117	YES	Technical Director	Farmers / Cooperatives	Italy
N118	YES	Intern on topic Ecophyto	Research community	France
N119	YES	Communication Manager - Agricultural business	Research community	Sweden
N120	YES		Research community	UK
N121	YES	Scientist	Research community	other - Europe
N122	YES	researcher	Research community	Latvia

Annex 5: List of participants - Webinar #2 Cover crops

Anonymized names	Attended?	Occupation	target group	country group
N1	YES	Post-Doc researcher	Research community	Italy
N2	YES	Advisor - Scuola Superiore S. Anna	Advisors / Consulting companies	Italy
N3	YES	Researcher at Policy and bioeconomy Centre of CREA (Rome)	Research community	Italy
N4	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	Italy
N5	YES	Sustainable viticulture coordinator	Agri-food industry	France
N6	YES	Conseillère viticulture	Advisors / Consulting companies	France
N7	YES	Agronomist	Citizens / Consumers	Greece
N8	YES	Conseiller environnement	Advisors / Consulting companies	France
N9	YES	Agronomists	Research community	Greece
N10	YES	Senior Consultant	Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europ
N11	YES	CEO	Agri-food industry	other - Europ
N12	YES	Product Manager	Agri-food industry	Italy
N13	YES	Researcher	Research community	Spain
N14	YES	Agroecologist	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N15	YES	Agronomist	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia
N16	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N17	YES	researcher	Research community	UK
N18	YES	agronomist	Research community	Greece
N19	YES	Administrator	Agri-food industry	Italy
N20	YES	Student	Research community	Italy
N21	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	Italy
N22	YES	Research Associate	Research community	Greece
N23	YES	Farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	Italy
N24	YES	Researcher	Research community	UK
N25	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	Italy
N26	YES	Horticultural Consultant	Research community	UK
N27	YES	AGRONOMIST	Research community	Greece
N28	YES	Agricultural advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N29	YES	Agronomist	Research community	Greece
N30	YES	Farm Advisor	Research community	UK
N31	YES	Researcher	Research community	Greece
N32	YES	Soil Biologist	Research community	UK
N33	YES	Farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N34	YES	Viticultural Consultant and Vineyard Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N35	YES	post-doctoral researcher	Research community	Italy
N36	YES	Agricultural Advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N37	YES	Farm Adviser	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N38	YES	Researcher	Research community	Spain
N39	YES	técnico de laboratorio -USC	Research community	Spain
N40	YES	Reseach	Research community	Spain
N41	YES	Investigador	Research community	Spain
N42	YES	Agricultural Advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N43	YES	research project manager	Research community	France
N44	YES	researcher	Research community	Latvia

Anonymized names	Attended?	Occupation	target group	country group
N45	YES	Farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	Spain
N46	YES	Skara	Research community	Sweden
N47	YES	Researcher	Research community	Sweden
N48	YES	Environmental engineer	Farmers / Cooperatives	France
N49	YES	Viticultura	Agri-food industry	Spain
N50	YES	Government scientist	Research community	UK
N51	YES	Agriculturist	Citizens / Consumers	Greece
N52	YES	Consultant	Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europ
N53	YES	Agricultural technical engineer, farm consultant	Farmers / Cooperatives	Spain
N54	YES	Technician	Agri-food industry	Spain
N55	YES	Technical Advisor Swedish board of Agriculture	Advisors / Consulting companies	Sweden
N56	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N57	YES	Agricultural journalist	other	France
N58	YES	Advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	Sweden
N59	YES	researcher	Research community	UK
N60	YES	Weed scientist	Research community	other - Europ
N61	YES	Researcher in Fruit Science - adaptation to climate change	Research community	other - Europ
N62	YES	Phd student	Citizens / Consumers	other - Europ
N63	YES	Agriculture	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia
N64	YES	owner	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia
N65	YES	Student	Research community	Italy
N66	YES	Research in Agriculture	Research community	Latvia
N67	YES	Flower farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N68	YES	Programme director	Research community	France
N69	YES	Project manager	other	other - Europ
N70	YES	Researcher	Research community	Greece
N71	YES	An agronomist, crop scientist	Research community	Latvia
N72	YES	Reseacher	Research community	other - Europ
N73	YES	Lead researcher	Research community	Latvia
N74	YES	Researcher	Research community	Latvia
N75	YES	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	Research community	Sweden
N76	YES	PhD student	Research community	Sweden
N77	YES	Researcher (soil & water)	Research community	other - Europ
N78	YES	researcher	Research community	Latvia
N79	YES	Advisor	Advisors / Consulting companies	other - Europ
N80	YES	leading researcher	Research community	Latvia
N81	YES	consultant of crop production	Advisors / Consulting companies	Latvia
N82	YES	Academic member at a university	Research community	non-Europe
N83	YES	Professor	Citizens / Consumers	non-Europe
N84	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	Latvia
N85	YES	Profesor Emérito Universidad de Santiago de Compostela	Research community	Spain
N86	YES	Agroecologist	Research community	France

Anonymized names	Attended?	Occupation	target group	country group
N87	YES	Estate manager	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N88	YES	Farm manager	Farmers / Cooperatives	UK
N89	YES	Agronomist	Advisors / Consulting companies	Italy
N90	YES	Researcher and farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	other - Europe
N91	YES	Senior Agri-Environment Consultant	Advisors / Consulting companies	UK
N92	YES	Advisor-researcher	Advisors / Consulting companies	Spain
N93	YES	Farmer	Farmers / Cooperatives	Latvia
N94	YES	Countryside Development Officer	other	other - Europe
N95	YES	researcher	Research community	UK
N96	YES	Phd student	Research community	Italy
N97	YES	Agronomist	Citizens / Consumers	Greece
N98	YES	Researcher	Research community	other - Europe
N99	YES	study and research farm	Research community	Latvia
N100	YES	NIBIO	other	other - Europe
N101	YES	Student	Research community	Greece
N102	YES	Researcher	Research community	Greece
N103	YES	Greek	Agri-food industry	Greece
N104	YES		Research community	France

